

IN PRIMARY CLASSES ,CONDUCTING LESSONS TO GIVE EFFECTIVE EDUCATION BY MEANS OF MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES.

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Annotation

The article highlights to build up the knowledge of primary school students by computer technologies that are commonly used today to conduct a lesson using it, as a consequence, to give effective knowledge and make them modern reach positive results with education.

Key words

Education, training, information and communication technologies, electronic presentations, exhibitions.

Science is the basement of development. Modern scientific achievements, innovative neither the state nor the society obtains a future that does not depend on ideas. Solly science and we are at the expense of enlightenment, intellectual potential, well-rounded person. We can give Uzbekistan as an example to a new stage of improvement.

Today's modern teacher is like developing a suitable generation is charged with an essential task and is aimed at improving the content of education putting tasks, keeping up with the times, modern education to get students' interest in their subject by introducing technologies and educational materials to the student with indifferent ways, psychological and pedagogical sides, modern information technologies, audio and video animations chances are utilized effectively. School in the education system of our country appropriately usage of ICT in teaching subjects is an urgent issue. Especially, the information technologies are wondered a universal device of education, not only students' knowledge, permits to organize skills and competencies, but also personal characteristics improve, satisfy their interest by learning. ICT is considerably developing.

Today, it is a credit module of all higher education institutions and schools can be a good example of this is the transition to the daily our system. Pedagogical and psychological studies impress that ICT obtains a huge impact on the improvement of students' theoretical, imaginative and reflexive thinking. A visual performance of this or that event or process in the student's memory is

educational development. That is to say , It enriches the material and aids it to be scientifically assimilated. From the introduction of information and communication technologies into the educational process the main target is teaching, which is characteristic of the modern information surrounding is the introduction of new kinds of activities.

It is thought that primary education is the foundation of the education system relies on the quality of education , and this is an elementary school the teacher obtains lots of responsibility. For a long time, education in this system, the primary school became a "school of skills", that is, every student obtains basic skills like reading, writing, counting for further education considered first stage of education that should be mastered. At this time , primary education is the child's first experience in the system is a testing ground for learning basic abilities need at this stage, improvement of activity, independence, punctual activity conditions for maintaining and introducing the child into the worldwide of education it is essential to create, make perfect its health and emotional characteristics. Implementation a person-oriented approach in education while using ICT, it became easy to rise, the possibility to productively manage the whole educational process seemed . Ready-made multimedia products and computer education during the lesson by some devices like Internet tools in educational and extracurricular activities multimedia educational programs and presentations, projects were introduced using it.

Information technologies may be utilized in all educational subjects. Learning and playing in classes the usage of programs is very productive. Primary school students using lots of various didactic materials, demonstration-exercise, control exercises as well as mixed computer programs with test modules involved prepared materials. In it, the current study and involvement of the rules of science on grammar-orthographic topics given in 3 ideas for repetition which the usage of well off and various materials will work appropriately.

In the years of using ICT, from 1st to 3rd grade, math , reading, a number of various tests on the mother tongue, almost all subjects and other academic subjects may be ready . Today, the lessons are not only printed, but also computerized , and it is essential to utilize tests. As long as , they are done, it is not impossible to get an immediate assessment gives, the evaluation is followed by the computer itself, on one or another topics allows them to definite their drawbacks. The Internet is available at the school helps us a lot in our work. Everybody knows that the Internet is a global information networking system . It's email, involves searching engines and

allows to access to different information resources will provide. Searching the essential information from it, re-improving it and multiplying it, install on all computers and being learned children independently in pairs, groups, and individually can be offered to work. Offer students a variety of assignments: the ability to making research, selecting the main one, making a presentation, filling in the table appears.

One of the other ways to gain information is directly from the Internet during the lesson to receive information. Searching for the necessary material in advance on the Internet, and in class. Dialogue on the studied material can be introduced in the form of Elementary school students should gain computer literacy the Internet independently choosing information, downloading it and making presentations or different types they know how to utilize it in their further work in the improvement and implementation of projects. A - second - grade school, students are not only in notebooks, but also smoothly on the computer can finish tasks. Students are the first to introduce with computers demands skills, continuously deepen their theoretical knowledge and they develop their effective abilities.

Informatics in the organization of the operational type of thinking in primary grades courses play an important role ..

This role of informatics is the organization of actions such as planning, searching for information, communication planning, building information models, in the form of a lot of of primary skills and competencies, like mediating activities which is considered. Assistant in computer reading, creativity, self-expression as well as comprehending is very essential by means of improvement. In primary school, students mastering the computer in terms of their activities, they can also be introduced in classes, using a computer lessons do not create obstacles for them. Essential aspects of information technology for the teacher and the student are :

- ✓ getting of the student's attention;
- ✓ making bigger the perception of information;
- ✓ inquisitiveness, creativity and individual activity;
- ✓ self- development

The role of lessons by using information technology in the teacher's work effected in the given chunks:

- ✓ proper giving of time;

- ✓ make sure that the content of the educational material is understandable and convincing
- ✓ develop the amount of information given;
- ✓ widening the kinds of educational tasks;
- ✓ creation of healthy competition, positive environment;
- ✓ regular development of professional qualifications.

As a conclusion, information communication technologies create students lots of opportunities to work on their skills independently. Additionally, it addresses for students , to search for information and learn so many things during this progress. They can make more things by using technologies to urge their knowledge. Technologies give a way to them to reach their aimed degree with ease.

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